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The meaning of “Being Art”: Perception and reality

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Abstract

Art and Science try to explore what we consider true. It does not depend on how reality is really, but actually on how we perceive it as humans. So, we create our own reality as we go through space basically. Our body is a good indicator. Art by all means, is the ability of the Being to investigate and create an intimate relationship with itself. Every action in life is art if it leads us to contemplate life with renewed eyes, and to perceive its incessant intelligent flow that blooms from our inner beauty. How many colors are there in our emotions towards reality perception? While contemplating reality, what kind of thoughts are we generating? Do they affect our state of consciousness?

Keywords: Perception; Consciousness; Reality; Art; Virus; Quantum

1. Introduction

Since we inhabited planet earth Art exists as the search for knowledge, meaning that people are artists and explorers just for a fact. When we realize the relationship between our inner world and our visualization of it, we turn art into a conscious act. A clear and lucid perception of reality gives us an orderly Image, our mental noise projections are reduced by the contemplation process itself [1]. Reality is shown as it is, this internal and spiral development process, leads us towards the discovery of what we are. Carl Jung said the creation of images is the way in which the psyche tries to fully understand the depths, leading consciousness to think, to think beyond itself. The progressive deployment of self-awareness delves into artistic and scientific expression, integrating the meditative state into process, giving it greater breathing and depth [2]. Art and science lived from the transpersonal gaze, does not have as its sole objective the mere production of forms, manuscripts, books, verses, statues, experiments; any act or work is considered artistic when it contains and is born from an expressive intention. From this perspective, the creative act becomes a door to self-discovery, self-awareness and contemplation. The intention of this manuscript is to inspire and help live Life as if it were a work of art in order to connect and enable our full Potential as Multidimensional Solar Human Beings.

1.1. Multidimensional

The inner world of our universe can be as complex as our imagination and thoughts can reach. Penetrating the deep fabric of reality, Lisa Randall offers a stunning insight into the possible hidden dimensions that our physical reality can make up [3]. The most recent theory extends to a higher dimension that occupy membranes of a wide range of configurations: they could be long, coiled tubes or infinitely long but infinitesimally thin sheets, or many other possible

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geometries. Mathematical spaces and dimensional contributions that lie in the deep and not directly perceptible inner reality of our universe are being subjected to intense exploration.

The true meaning of the word quantum (quantum) in physics refers to a minimum unit of matter or energy in a transfer process. However, we use the term quantum interchangeably with multidimensionality. The possible reason why this term took on this popular meaning was that most of physics refers to things that are in a pure, empirical state. However, the theory of quantum mechanics gave us the beginning of understanding things that appeared to be in a random, haphazard, or chaotic state. This randomness or probability-based reality can only be as we perceive it and not at all random by the standards of new laws of physics that we do not yet have or understand.

Figure 1 "Untitled" from the visions series

When we go through interdimensional physics, which includes energies of what we call spirituality, we discover something that we were not expecting, not only because it is in a quantum state, but because it contains something more of which the coherent science of third dimension does not want to accept: Intelligence in physics. Everything that is interdimensional is aligned with creation. Astronomers are starting to talk about intelligent designs [4]. We are realizing that the quantum aspect of the universe could actually have consciousness. We do live with parameters and attributes of space that statistically continue to go against all probabilities, we are on a planet, in a universe full of life, it is microbial, yes, and it represents the initial attributes of unicellular life [5,6].

1.2. Invisible but real

We now recognize the vital role that viruses acquired, mobile genetic elements have played in evolutionary and developmental processes within the genomes of species [7,8,9]. Viral infections and subviral RNAs (such as microRNAs) can enter the host genome and persist as genetic regulatory networks [10,11,12,13].

All mammals and non-human primates rely on olfaction, that is, chemoreception as basis of the sense of smell for social recognition, group behavior, and the coordination of organized social life. Human beings developed other ways to establish social bonds. Günther Witzany proposed several waves of infection by endogenous retroviruses caused, loss or damage of receptors, olfactory genes and related tissues in human ancestors, favoring a change of dominance to other sensory modalities, and in particular, to vision and vocalization [14]. So in humans, the pheromone-based social bond typical to other mammals was replaced by a more complex cognitive process, an extended mind and emotional networks based on recursive thoughts and feelings, and the ability to generate and transfer information to others. Myths from the past and cultural traditions, such as ritual groups, techniques from related cults, such as painting and music, became essential tools in the transgenerational transfer of memory and group learning [15,16,17,18]. On the other hand, Vladimir Poponin and Peter Gariaev, a Russian research team of geneticists and linguistics, have scientifically documented how DNA repairs with the ability of sound and light [19,20,21,22]. Poponin's research demonstrated that DNA has the ability to attract photons, and yielded unexpected results on several levels. In a study chamber, the polarization and orientation states of light waves, known as Photons, were measured.

As expected, these light waves moved randomly in the Experimental Chamber. Then he put DNA inside the Chamber and measured the photons again. To his surprise and exceeding all his expectations, the presence of DNA had strongly organized the light waves, so that they formed a coherent pattern, which suggested that the DNA produced a field profoundly powerful that forcefully organized the space around it. Regarding sound, other research found that it may be possible to activate DNA through conscious linguistic expressions [23]: using sound-words as well as intentions-thoughts. These, are forms of electromagnetic energy, so they would have the power to modify human bio-energy fields, which in turn can affect the anatomy and physiology of the body. Valerie Hunt argues that the mind exists in the dimension of electromagnetic fields,

Figure 2 "Untitled" from the visions series

rather than residing in the brain [24]. In 2021, a study was published on the effects of listening to music on gene regulation through micro-RNA sequencing of listeners and their controls without exposure to music. Upregulation of 6 micro-RNAs and downregulation of 2 micro-RNAs were identified in the music group. It was reported that some upregulated micro-RNAs respond to neuronal activity and modulate their plasticity, myelination of the nervous system. central and cognitive functions such as memory and long-term potentiation. No significant changes in micro-RNA

expressions associated with music education or low musical aptitude were detected [25,26,27]. At the University of Glasgow, a group of researchers was able to detect sound waves that run through the entire structure of DNA and are imperceptible to the human ear [28]. Therefore, sound is an epigenetic modulator that can affect human genes, their regulation and health status. This would indicate that DNA is not simply a genetic storage medium that serves as a heritable "blueprint" and an evolutionary protocol, but that it is also a species-specific ecological niche and also functions as a structure for the reception and transmission of electromagnetic energy (of more than 90%) in the field of light (bioelectric) and sound (bioacoustic) signaling [29,30].

1.3. Consciousness and energy

The entire existence is filled with energy that is responsive, that is alive, that is intelligent, vibrant, flexible and telepathic, and considering that we are part of it, you are also brimming with these qualities. As the solar system travels through the depths of space, traversing terrain filled with highly energetic cosmic radiation, it is filled with a seemingly limitless network of blueprints of consciousness [31]. This causes a rain of energy that continually falls on the earth and provides it with large quantities of atomic particles that penetrate the cells and atoms of all things to transmit a form of electricity full of vital energy. Ancient cultures often said that the soft spot on a baby's skull was the gate to heaven, as they knew it was a gateway for the flow of cosmic energy and spiritual intelligence to the cranial ganglia. Cosmic radiation recharges the central nervous system with life force energy and acts as a visible extension of the physical nervous system to facilitate connection to the greater cosmos.

Currently, the massive increase of radiation from cosmos allows humanity to acquire a more transcendent vision of existence [31]. The presence of these mysterious cosmic energies were detected long ago and named by various cultures such as The unified field Ki, Chi, prana, energy, orgone, ether, life force, pneuma, force and cosmic radiation. The Hippocratic vision of the respiratory system is curious, the air does not reach the lungs through the trachea, the pneuma first goes to the brain through some channels and from there it passes to the belly, which transfers it to the lungs following the veins of the body [32]. Pneuma is the mediator of the relationship between heart and brain according Greek medicine. Starting with the Stoics, the pneuma was interpreted as that part of the world that enters matter, the body and gives it life and movement, it is the bridge between the physical and the non-material (spirit, soul). We use this energy throughout our lives to project our being, since it is an unlimited source of power. Within our particular field of experience, our thoughts, feelings, and desires are the primary materials that we use to create our world.

The power of creation resides in all forms of consciousness and consciousness exists in a state of supreme cooperation throughout all existence. Consciousness is existence. Love is the primordial material source, it is a pulsating cosmic vibration energy that fuels every aspect of the existence field [33].

Consciousness and energy are the two essential aspects of deepest reality; A few years ago, the physicist Richard Feynman expressed: "...in physics we currently do not have true knowledge of what energy is" referring to the fact that the conservation of energy is an abstract mathematical principle, and there is no concrete notion of what is energy [34]. In this sense, science recognizes its limits, it is dedicated to describe reality rather than finding meaning or the meaning of things. In this case, a reality model is not enough, since as human beings we experience an intense and vivid relationship with energy, which we seek to understand at a level that makes sense with our subjective experience of it, that is, our energy awareness [35]. For traditional cultures, energy is not an abstract, invisible or remote notions, it is rather an everyday reality that permeates all dimensions of existence.

1.4. Change of rhythms, change of bodies

When flow of life changes its rhythm, you have to change your body. It is not just an idea or a social change. A series of changes are taking place on a planetary scale within thoughts, emotions, sex, human physiology in general we still do not understand well what they define, transition phases, dangerous swings of current life between the abysses, underground of elemental forces and the highest peaks of cosmic consciousness. Let's look at some changes that are taking place: in the mind fields, when consciousness uses knowledge to reach higher and higher fields of meaning, a mental instrument serves the purposes of Being. But if knowledge reaches an end on itself at the service of power, vision is lost (pathology of consciousness) and mind functions lead us onto a mechanical brain. The mental critical point is reached when consciousness identifies itself with knowledge.

In the feeling zone, if love uses emotions in search of increasing deeper feelings, the emotional instrument acquires full function as norm; But if emotions are constituted as a stopping point on themselves (currently happening, in which the being is transformed into an emotion consumer) the ability to feel the unity of life is lost (pathology of love), the ability to feel the difference between good and bad, dullness of feeling, existential apathy. Then, the critical limit is reached when love (the force that allows transformation) is identified with emotions. In the sexual field, when sex is put at the

service of the creative forces of life, it acquires plenitude as an instrument. But from the moment it is constituted as an end in itself (as an autonomous force unrelated to conscience, ethics and love) then sex stops serving life and becomes a force of destruction: instead of create life, it feeds. Of life (voracity of possession and consumption). Therefore, the critical limit is reached when the creative energy of the being is identified with sex [36].

Modern neurophysiology, as a result of a research of PK Anojin. N.A Bernshtein, AN Leontiev, AR Luria, belonging to the Soviet school, and the Americans Bárbara Brown, Robert Ornstein and collaborators, allows us to affirm that the human brain is an organ with sufficient flexibility to allow the formation of complex functional systems without a fixed material base, but relying on a configuration of organic zones whose structure varies according to the different stages of ontogenesis and the psychic activity developed in social experience [36]. In other words, the conscious and voluntary action of the psyche can form new functional structures. Indeed, psychologist Ernest Rossi also explored the revolutionary implications of discoveries in genetics and neuroscience on the daily lives of humans. In "The Psychobiology of Gene Expression," he discusses the tremendous application potential of consciously motivated behavior, subjective mental states, and our PERCEPTION of choice and free will in regulating gene expression to optimize health [37]. Likewise, another group demonstrated that DNA undergoes a helical change from the normal conformation of DNA B to DNA Z in Alzheimer's disease and this alters genetic orientation and function. Thus, the DNA helix is modified depending on brain function and stress [38].

We have expanded our perception limits. It places us in a new environment which allows unknown frequency levels (or light) to enter our own fields, to make us aware of their existential reality. These must be recreated by our imagination and expressed through out newer myths and languages within this newly perceived world, in which there is potential only, until the new consciousness level can provide some kind of form to these new frequencies. This is our greatest achievement to Create a brand new reality.

But now we are penetrating even deeper in search of our own way to be, that is, an ultra interior field where human beings can move freely as breathing, without ceasing to be. This new field already is here we just have to learn to live in it. And this requires a new rebirth, a conversion of human physiology not only a Metanoia, but a metachemical or Alchemical resonance between spirit and matter [39]. The important thing is that we realize that it is not possible to make this trip between the two worlds with the same body that we have today. Castaneda in Don Juan's mouth constantly refers to this wonderful transition between The World of concrete forms and The World of formless consciousness (between the Tonal and the Nahual) and all of the teacher's teaching points towards the art of dance between those two worlds: being a two-faced warrior and being able to look in two directions [40].

Figure 3 "Untitled" from the visions series

1.5. The door of perception: the heart

Historically, the heart was considered one of the throne of the mind. Most ancient cultures were cardiocentric. However, in the last 200 years, science leaned towards a materialist, mechanistic and reductionist vision, limiting the heart to simply being a hydraulic pump used to oxygenate the blood and carry it to all parts of the body. The brain became the throne of the mind, that is, of thoughts and emotions. However, in recent decades, studies have increased confirming that the heart changes its rhythm very subtly when we experience an emotion or a thought, it is not absolutely rhythmic, it has flexibility. This flexibility is called cardiac variability because it has been seen that our heart changes and this variability is greater when we get excited, when we think there is greater cognitive capacity, memory increases, our verbal fluency increases, attention increases, for example, expert meditators have greater heart variability. In the 16th century, Paracelsus stated that language does not belong to the tongue, but to the heart. Let me hear you speak and I will tell you what your heart is like. It is well known that the interaction between the brain and the heart is mediated by the vagus nerve that communicates throughout our body, thus returning to the heart as the door to perception. We perceive and understand the World around us [32]. We are more aware of stimulus around us, on greater way the brain response to the heartbeat. This response in the brain of the heart these matches has allowed us to design a new model which we understand the interdependent dynamics of what is subjective perception (self-awareness), the internal representation of reality (external world) where the respiratory system participates. A study published in 2018 showed for the first time the neuroanatomical pathways of breathing. In this study, what was seen is that the respiratory pattern (in addition to the olfactory process) influences the areas of the brain most involved in attention, memory, cognitive, emotional processing and behavior [41,42,32].

In 2014, Catherine Tallon-Baudry and her group published a study that shows that perception is influenced by the heart, it was stated that we see an object if our brain responds to the heartbeat, otherwise, that object will go unnoticed [43]. So, who marks perception, the brain or the signals from the heart? Tallon-Baudry and her group have shown that the heart influences the perception of any stimulus, not just those that awaken emotions in us. The results showed that when the heart beats we move our eyes more in search of relevant information. The heart is not only a perceptive doorway it also sets the pace of entry. When the heart contracts and blood flows into the body, systole, our eyes search for the most relevant information among The World that observes. These random-looking movements represent competition for attention resources. When the heart expands, diastole, we soak up the information we selected as relevant when it emptied. That is, ascending cardiac signals to the brain play an important role in moderating cognitive processes. The heartbeat sets the rate at which we perceive [44].

As we know the more the brain responds to the heartbeat, the more we think about ourselves. This is when we imagine or recreate an image were we are protagonists, communication between heart and brain is stronger. However, meditation is a time during which we are the object of observation, of listening. Meditation is not intellectual or emotional interpretation of oneself. When you start meditating the interaction between the brain and the heart decreases. During meditation, the identity is set aside. Dogen Zenji, founder of the Soto school of the Zen Buddhist tradition, already recited, "to know oneself is to forget oneself." From the schools of Alexandria to the Middle Ages, the heart has always had a close correspondence with morality, with the judgment that we carry within. Studies done in Japan, the degree of empathy reported verbally by participants was correlated with neural responses to the heart. The compassionate heart also manifests in the brain. Thus, the brain of those who express themselves as racist responds strongly to the heart. Also, the brain of those who manifest compassion responds strongly to the heart.

The heart displays what is inside [45]. According to António Damásio's studies, those who know his body sensations best make better decisions. On the other hand, we know that emotion is a complicated process that takes time to prepare. During this time, the elaboration is not conscious, but we know that the body sensations inform us of what is brewing inside. Bodily sensations are a sense that informs us about ourselves when thought is blinded. An idea materializes in sensations and bodily states, an aggressive word, a stressful email or a smile produce changes in the body and vice versa, the brain receives the body's sensations, which are not very healthy, and classifies them. Cultivating habits that display bodily states that the brain associates as positive is also taking care of mental health. The sensations of the body can also help us recover emotions that time or its harshness have hidden. Francois Rabelais reminds us that science without consciousness is nothing more than the ruin of the soul.

The heart is the only reality. The mind is just a transitory phase. To remain as "Self" is to enter the heart. Ramana Maharshi

Figure 4 "Untitled" from the visions series

1.6. Perception and reality

The great magicians, knowing deeply the laws of the physical world, created illusions in the senses, levitating objects or cutting people before our eyes. This is how they deceive our perception.

Yoshi Oida, a Japanese theater actor, tells how his desire to become invisible like ninjas led him to become an actor. These, acting in relation to natural laws, make us see that they walk on water or become invisible. In traditional Japanese theater, there is a gesture called pointing at the moon. There are many actors who perform this movement with true precision and mastery, but only a few manage to make you see the moon, creating a perception in the viewer through the illusion of becoming invisible.

1.6.1. What is perception?

According to Kabbalah, the principle of whirlpools (Rashit ha galgalim) is the beginning of creative activity. Through the sphere of Keter, the crown, the highest sphere of the Tree of life, the creative essence comes into manifestation, unfolding in a double whirlpool of expansion and contraction, , through this dance, between the centrifugal and centripetal quality. of energy all existence is expressed.

To have knowledge and experience of itself, to be able to know itself, self-observe, this creative essence needs a system that allows it to feel itself, this is from the origin, the seed of perception is involved in creation. This first manifestation of swirls generates a sensitive electromagnetic field, a cosmic neural tube, the germ of our exquisitely evolved nervous system. In human embryos, the first thing to manifest is the nervous system. It is our most important system. Without perception there is no experience through which our consciousness can evolve.

In the Sefer Yetsirah, book that narrates creation, it is said that divinity creates his universe with 32 wisdom paths. These pathways are related to our nervous system. 31 paths correspond to the 31 pairs of nerves that are originated from the spinal cord. Path 32 corresponds to the entire complex of cranial nerves, which are 12 pairs.

This book describes the structure of the Tree of Life, which represents the entire cosmos, macro and micro, and expresses the design of each particle of existence.

The 31 nerves of the spinal cord are linked to the sense of touch. And the 12 cranial nerves to the senses of sight, taste, hearing and smell. Through the nervous system, information from the outside reaches our brain and can be decoded into an emotional, three-dimensional experience. From our brain we can respond to our environment through our body, our emotion, our speech.

From another point of view, we know that our energetic anatomy is an extension of our nervous, sympathetic and parasympathetic systems [46]. Through our energetic anatomy we are part of La Lattice, the great cosmic grid, the great field of cosmic experience, the network that connects everything [47].

In many ancient cultures of America it is customary to speak with stones, trees, rivers, mountains. In the West we consider it a poorly evolved or animistic trait.

In an investigation into water movements, Theodor Schwenk discovered that "all movements that nature uses to generate its innumerable creatures are found in the human larynx." [48]. That is to say, it has the ability to print in the air through voice all possible forms of creation.

We can think then that nature keeps within itself the entire code of the creation dance.

The primordial essence and sensitivity are then in every particle of existence.

The receptive capacity of our nervous system is its feminine aspect. Among the basic functions that we have banished from our patriarchal culture are contemplation, listening, and non-action.

Reconnecting with nature wisdom, communication with the earth and the environment will allow us to expand the limits of our perception. Dance and dream with everything that exists. With the stars and the forests. Reunify in the integration of all opposites, the thinking brain and the feeling brain, to awaken the neural network of the heart. The new brain that will allow us to enable new senses, since the only way to access a new dimension is to develop the appropriate tuner.

Remember from the consciousness of elements, their movements and geometries, the very essence, the mystery and the Unity of life.

2. Conclusion

The new rhythm is a liberation dance, the Being oscillates between matter and antimatter, and between consciousness and purposefulness, between the infinite and the infinitesimal, generating and dissolving forms, absorbing and releasing energy, encoding and decoding meanings. Not theories, but human functions imagining and representing can ensure the future of the human race, giving form to a brand new reality. Achieving a development cycle, an enigmatic impulse from the Pituitary gland that resonates in the other glands of internal secretion and unleashes a physiological storm in the human body. Awakening heart intelligence. Something analogous is happening in the planetary body and in order to correctly interpret the new signs, it is important that we realize that the change does not begin in the political, economic or cultural centers of the modern world, but in the geomagnetic centers of the Earth that it constitutes the primordial alimony that animates the still invisible forms of cosmic Humanity.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Author Contributions

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References

- [1] Castañeda MA, Amato R, Sepulveda CS, Carlucci MJ. The evolution of Knowledge: From Inert to Living Sciences. *Global Journal Ecology* 2022, 7(2): 082-089. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17352/gje.000066>. 2022.
- [2] Diemanz Hartz M, Carlucci MJ. Sapere aude: Towards a brand new humanity. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 2023,18(01), 1128–1132. Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.1.0749>
- [3] Randall L. *Warped passages: Unraveling the Mysteries of Universe’s Hidden Dimensions*. Ed. Ecco. USA.2006
- [4] Steele EJ, Reginald M. Gorczyński RM, Lindley RA, Liu Y, Temple R, Tokoro G, Wickramasinghe DT, Chandra Wickramasinghe N. Lamarck and Panspermia - On the Efficient Spread of Living Systems Throughout the Cosmos. *Progress in Biophysics and Molecular Biology* 2019,149, pp10-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pbiomolbio.2019.08.010>
- [5] Castañeda MA, Sepulveda CS, Carlucci MJ. The Omnipresent Power of the Invisible: from Visuses to Being Conscient. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 2021, 12(02), 518–525. Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2021.12.2.0617> eISSN: 2581-9615
- [6] Wainwright M, Wickramasinghe NC. *Life comes from space: the Decisive evidence*. World Scientific Publishing. 2022. DOI: 10.1142/13140
- [7] Weiner AM. SINEs and LINEs: Troublemakers, saboteurs, benefactors, ancestors. In R. F. Gesteland, T. R. Cech, & J. F. Atkins (Eds.), *The RNA World* (3rd ed). (pp. 507–533). 2006. New York: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press.
- [8] Villarreal LP. Virolution can help us understand the origin of life. In V. Kolb. Ed., *Handbook of astrobiology* 2015, pp. 421–440. Boca Raton: CrC Press
- [9] Roossinck MJ. Metagenomics of plant and fungal viruses reveals an abundance of persistent lifestyles. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2015, 5, 1–3.
- [10] Bushman FD. Targeting survival: Integration site selection by retroviruses and LTR-retrotransposons. *Cell* 2003, 115, 135–138
- [11] Mitchell RS, Beitzel BF, Schroder AR, Shinn P, Chen H, Berry CC, Ecker JR, Bushman FD. Retroviral DNA integration: ASLV, HIV, and MLV show distinct target site preferences. *PLoS Biology* 2004, 2(8), 1127–1137.
- [12] Lambowitz, A. M., Zimmerly, S. Group II introns: Mobile ribozymes that invade DNA. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology* 2011,3(8), 1–19.
- [13] Artuso MC, Roldán JS, Scolaro LA, Carlucci MJ. Viruses: as mediators in “elan vital” of the creative evolution. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2016, 46:78-84 doi:10.1016/j.meegid.2016.10.028
- [14] Witzany G. How viruses made us humans. *The Oxford Handbook of Human Symbolic Evolution*. Edited by N. Gontier, A. Lock, and C. Sinha. 2021. DOI: 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198813781.013.5
- [15] Tomasello, M. *The cultural origins of human cognition*. 1999. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- [16] Zilhão, J., Angelucci, D. E., Badal-García, E., d’Errico, F., Daniel, F., Dayet, L., Douka, K., Higham, T. F., Martínez-Sánchez, M. J., Montes-Bernárdez, R., Murcia-Mascarós, S., Pérez-Sirvent, C., Roldán-García, C., Vanhaeren, M., Villaverde, V., Wood, R., Zapata, J. Symbolic use of marine shells and mineral pigments by Iberian Neandertals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA* 2010,107, 1023–1028.

- [17] Montagu J. How music and instruments began: A brief overview of the origin and entire development of music, from its earliest stages. *Frontiers in Sociology* 2017, 2(8), 1-12.
- [18] Hoffmann DL, Standish CD., García-Diez M, Pettitt PB, Milton JA, Zilhão J, Alcolea-González JJ, Cantalejo-Duarte P, Collado H, de Balbín, R, Lorblanchet, M., Ramos-Muñoz J, Weniger GCh, Pike AWG. U-Th dating of carbonate crusts reveals Neandertal origin of Iberian cave art. *Science* 2018, 359, 912-915.
- [19] Gariaev PP, Chudin VI, Komissarov GG, Berezin AA, Vasiliev AA. Holographic Associative Memory of Biological Systems, *Proceedings SPIE - The International Society for Optical Engineering. Optical Memory and Neural Networks*. 1991 v.1621 p.280- 291. USA.
- [20] Gariaev PP, Grigor'ev KV, Vasil'ev AA, Poponin VP, Shcheglov VA. Investigation of the Fluctuation Dynamics of DNA Solutions by Laser Correlation Spectroscopy. *Bulletin of the Lebedev Physics Institute*, 1992 n.11-12, p. 23-30
- [21] Poponin V. The DNA phatom effect: direct measurement of a new field in the vacuum substructure, *Ann. Conf. on Treatment and Res. Experienced Anomalous Trauma*, 1995, San Rafael, CA.
- [22] Gariaev P, Friedman MJ, Leonova-Gariaeva EA. Principles of linguistic-wave genetics. *DNA Decipher Journal* 2011, 1,1 pp.11-24
- [23] Luckman S. *Conscious healing with the regenetics TM method: Book one of the regenetics TM series*. 1st ed. 2005. ISBN: 1591138434.
- [24] Hunt V. *Infinite mind: Science of the human vibrations of consciousness*. Malibu Publishing Company 2000; ISBN: 9780964398801.
- [25] Sathianarayana Rao TS, Jagannatha KS, Asha MR. Drooping genes vs dancing genes. *India Journal Psychiatry*. 2009, 51(3):167-168
- [26] Kanduri C, Raijas P, Ahvenainen M, Philips AK, Ukkola-Vuoti L, Lähdesmäki H, Järvelä I. The effect of listening to music on human transcriptome. *Peer J*. 2015 3:e830
- [27] Sasidhraran Nair P, Raijas P, Ahvenainen M, Philips AK, Ukkola-Vuoti L, Järvelä I. Music-listening regulates human microRNA expression. *Epigenetics* 2021,16(5):554-566
- [28] González-Jiménez M, Ramakrishnan G, Harwood T, Laphorn AJ, Kelly SM, Ellis EM, Wynne K. Observation of coherent delocalized phonon-like modes in DNA under physiological conditions. *Nature Communications* 2016, 7, 11799. DOI 10.1038/ncomms11799
- [29] de Koning APJ, Gu W, Castoe TA, Batzer MA, Pollock DD. 2011. Repetitive elements may comprise over two-thirds of the human genome. *PLoS Genetics* 2011, 7(12), 1-12.
- [30] Villarreal LP, Witzany G. When competing viruses unify: Evolution, conservation, and plasticity of genetic identities. *Journal of Molecular Evolution* 2015, 80, 30
- [31] www.5dearthproject.com/space-weather-tools/
- [32] Castellanos N. *Neuroscience of the body. How the body sculpts the brain*. 2022. Editorial Kairos
- [33] Marciniak B. *Take back the power. Pleiadian Wisdom for a world in chaos*. Edit. Obelisco. 2007.
- [34] Feynman R. *The Feynman lectures on physics*. Vol 1, Chapter 4: Conservation of energy. 2013. www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu
- [35] Aberastury F. *Writings. Conscious system for movement technique*. Publisher Catalogs 1992.
- [36] Muñoz Soler RP. *Synthetic anthropology. Signs, rhythms and functions of the planetary human*. 1980. Ediciones Depalma, Buenos Aires
- [37] Rossi E. *The psychobiology of gene expression: Neuroscience and neurogenesis in hypnosis and the healing arts*. Edit. W.W. Norton and Company. 2002. ISBN 0393703436
- [38] Suram A, Jagannatha KS, Latha KS, Viswamitra MA. First evidence to show the topological change of DNA from B-DNA to Z-DNA conformation in the hippocampus of Alzheimer's brain. *J Neuromolecular Med* 2002,2:287-95.
- [39] Castañeda MA, Sepulveda C, Carlucci MJ. In *Time of global planetary challenges: Metanoia*. Austin Anthropol. 2020,4(1): 1016. ISSN: 2768-0258
- [40] Castañeda C. *Stories of power*. Fund of Economic Culture. 1976, Mexico.

- [41] Zelano C, Jiang H, Zhou G, Arora N, Schuele S, Rosenow J, Gottfried J. Nasal respiration entrains human limbic oscillations and modulates cognitive function. *J. Neuroscience*, 2016,36(49):12448-12467
- [42] Wegener B, Croy I, Hähner A, Hummel T. Olfactory training with older people. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*. 2018, 33(1):212-220
- [43] Park HD, Correia S, Ducorps A, Tallon-Baudry C. Spontaneous fluctuations in neural responses to heartbeats predict visual detection. *Nature Neuroscience* 2014, 17(4)612-618
- [44] Babo-Rebelo M, Richter CG, Tallon.Baudry C. Neural responses to heartbeats in the default network encode the self in spontaneous thoughts. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 2016,36;7829-7840
- [45] Zhu J, Ji L, Li C. Heart rate variability monitoring for emotion and disorders of emotion. *Physiological Measures* 2019, 40(6):064004
- [46] Dubro P F, Lapierre D. *Consciousness frameworks: Multidimensional evolution* 2011. Edit. Vesica Piscis
- [47] Grinberg-Zylberbaum J. *The creation of the experience. The syntergic theory* 1988. Edit. I.P.E.C.
- [48] Schwenk T. *Sensitive chaos: the creation of flowing forms in water and air*. 2014. Edit Rudolf Steiner Press